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From Bureaucratic Organization to Team of Teams: A Case Study from The Provincial Government of West Java

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Abstract

To face increasingly complex challenges and environments, public organizations are transforming from being bureaucratic and rigid to being more agile. Researchers have not widely discussed the agility of public organizations in the context of Team of Teams. This study reveals how the practice of implementing Team of Teams in public organizations in the Indonesian context. The findings show that public organizations with a Team of Teams approach emphasize more on the formation and collaboration of competency-based groups. These findings provide insight for other public organizations to implement the Team of Teams approach.

Keywords: West Java, Indonesia, Public Organization, Agile Organization

1. Introduction

In today's challenging and complex environment, traditional organizations often struggle to meet customer demands. Hence, public and non-public organizations transform from traditional organizations into agile organizations to provide better value to their customers (Silva-Martinez, 2024). By definition, traditional organizations are organizations that apply rigid bureaucratic principles with a focus on the authority, role, and responsibility of each position (McCartney & Alisa Lê, 2024). On the other hand, an agile organization is the type of organization that gives fast response to changes in the environment, like technology changes and customer needs changes (Janssen & van der Voort, 2020). There are several terms used in the previous literature that refer to agility at an organizational level, namely business agility (Revutska & Maršiková, 2021), enterprise agility (Tyszkiewicz & Pawlak-Wolanin, 2017), and organizational agility (Khristianto et al., 2024). In the context of public organization, the organization often has a hierarchical and bureaucratic structure. Public organizations need flexibility and responsivity by implementing agile principles to face challenges like policy change, people's demands, and unpredictable crisis (Ramirez-Barrera & Rojas-Berrio, 2024). On the other hand, agile principles are difficult to implement in large organizations because of their complexity (Magistretti et al., 2019).

Agile organizations have been a topic of many research articles since the 1990s. Most research on agile organizations has focused largely on knowledge infrastructure (Becker, 2001), on organizational culture (Ghasemi et al., 2017), or on leadership, either technological leadership (Doghri & Chteoui, 2023) or entrepreneurial leadership (Fadhil et al., 2023). Studies on agile organization emphasize the principles of agile organization and describe how important agile organizational leadership is. For example, Denning (2016) mentioned three laws that become characteristic of agile organizations, namely, The Law of the Small Team, The Law of the Customer, and The Law of the Network. Little is known about the relationship between the competencies or skills possessed by the people involved in an agile organization. On the other hand, the transformation from traditional organizations to agile organizations is also a concern for public organizations in Indonesia.

Initially, most public organizations in Indonesia adopted a bureaucratic structure, distinguished by three to four tiers of echelon within their top management hierarchy. Additionally, bureaucratic simplification has been implemented in Indonesia intensively since 2019, along with the vision of President Joko Widodo to decrease bureaucratic structure (Saksono et al., 2024). In this program, structural positions, especially echelons III and IV, are replaced with functional positions focusing on skills and competencies (Sahid et al., 2019; Umar et al., 2019). While bureaucratic simplification provides various benefits to make faster and more accurate public services, the practice brings another innovation that public organizations perform (Saputra et al., 2023). Therefore, one of the innovations is to transform from a traditional organization or command team with a bureaucratic structure to a design-centric organization called a Team of Teams (McChrystal et al., 2015; Young et al., 2016), as shown in Figure 1. Team of Teams is an approach in which many small, autonomous teams work synergistically and it is another form of agile organization (De Vries et al., 2016). Unlike a command team, which has a hierarchical structure, centralized decision-making process, top-down communication, and silo mentality, a Team of Teams has the opposite characteristic. Team of Teams tend to have semi-hierarchical structures prioritizing cross-function collaboration, more inclusive, and promoting a creative culture (Aghina et al., 2018).

Figure 1: Transforming from command team to Team of Teams

Source: Adapted from McChrystal et al., 2015

One of the causes of this institutional transformation is that public organizations operate in a complex environment (Tran, 2023b). For instance, public organizations frequently encounter significant obstacles, including poverty, education, and health, which are characterized by a multitude of causes and intricate solutions. Furthermore, a cross-sectoral approach is necessary due to the interlinkages of numerous public issues, including poverty, which have an impact on education and health (Guillaume & Loufrani-Fedida, 2023).

To the best of our knowledge, there is no prior research that has investigated the use of a Team of Teams approach in public organizations, especially in the Indonesia context. Consequently, the objective of this investigation is to develop a practical Team of Teams model that is appropriate for public organizations in the Indonesian context. This study of the implementation of Team of Teams in public organizations focuses on the conditions before and after the implementation of Team of Teams. Subsequently, this investigation will endeavor to resolve the subsequent inquiry: "What is the model of Team of Teams implementation for public organizations in Indonesia?" The study commences with a literature review that delineates the concept of the Team of Teams in order to address the research questions. The research methods, findings, discussion, analysis, and conclusion are then elaborated upon. Also, we provide recommendations for future research and discuss the limitations of the current study.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Agile Organization

The business sector is increasingly recognizing the importance of adopting more agile and flexible organizational models to facilitate increased competitiveness in complex and dynamic contexts (Bushe, 2021; Pardo-Fernández et al., 2024). For example, Khristianto et al. (2024) highlight the necessity for organizations within the tourism sector to adjust to the business landscape prompted by the Fourth Industrial Revolution and the COVID-19 pandemic. The data were obtained from 175 directors or managers of tour operators. In this case, the manager of tour operators has built their skills in the context of market sensing capability and innovation.

Vaszkun & Sziráki (2023) identified that agile organizations must maintain alignment between aspects of structure, culture, and leadership so that these three vital elements can work together well. Denning (2016) also argued that agile organizations should develop small autonomous cross-functional teams that can deliver value to customers. In public organizations, leadership direction serves as a framework for addressing difficulties and delivering services to the community (Tran, 2023a). A leader in a public organization can serve as an innovator and a catalyst for fostering collaboration inside the organization (Jensen et al., 2023). The establishment of an improved organizational structure and culture is feasible under the leadership guidelines outlined in the legislation (Almahasneh et al., 2023).

Kiziloglu et al. (2023) studied 325 samples who are working in the finance sector of Turkey and found that an effective leadership strategy assists staff in navigating challenges and transitions that arise both inside and outside the organization. Moreover, Fadhil et al. (2023) examined 329 middle managers in Iraqi organizations and determined that a leader's entrepreneurial attributes, supported by transparent and effective communication abilities, significantly contribute to the development of a more agile work team. Effective leadership, bolstered by responsible leadership, can enable organizations to maintain agility and ultimately attain sustainable performance (Dharmawan et al., 2024). Further research can create a model that explains the impact of leadership style on sustainable performance.

2.2. Team of Teams

There are few studies about the implementation of Team of Teams approach. Strictly speaking, we found only seventeen such empirical studies. Based on existing literature, the Team of Teams approach can be used in educational environments by fostering a collaborative culture grounded in trust, a shared goal, intentional communication, and interconnectivity (Young et al., 2016). This type of model also emphasizes the importance of collaboration between all elements of education, including faculty, staff, and parents of students, in order to achieve higher levels of achievement. Prior studies about Team of Teams also tended to focus more on the routing and scheduling problem (Zamorano & Stolletz, 2017). The mathematical model developed considers the diverse skills of each team member along with the necessary time limitations. In addition to the mathematical model, the horizontal and vertical coordination models created by Davison et al. (2012) can describe the relationship between the integration team, point team, and support team where the team plays leadership an important role in team performance.

In the context of sports, Haxhnikaj et al. (2023) found that the Team of Teams culture also plays an important role in preventing discrimination against any team member. Their extensive study comprised a sample of 237 athletes from the Kosovo National Team of Team Sports, consisting of 118 males and 119 females. They recommend that the respective federations, sports trainers, and relevant sports authorities need to work together as a Team of Teams to prevent discrimination. However, it is not clear who is the leader of the three parties. Likewise, Henriksen (2015) added insight into Team of Teams in the world of sports by paying attention to the psychological side of team members in dealing with conditions before and after the match. According to their research, three essential components for sustaining the positive psychology of athletes are: 1. Remaining present, 2. Embracing a diverse array of thoughts and emotions, and 3. Articulating personal values while committing to behave in accordance with those beliefs.

3. Method

This study uses a single case study to understand the complex dynamics that occur at the organization and formulate a conceptual model. A single case study is an in-depth research approach to a unique case in order to understand a particular phenomenon (Yin, 2018). Using this method, we collected data using semi-structured interviews with a list of questions that we had created and related to the topic. Furthermore, we collected data from other sources, such as through observation and Focus Group Discussion (FGD). We then made field notes in an organized manner as a case study database. To check the validity and reliability of the research, we built a strong narrative to support the findings and created a detailed research guide. We followed Yin's steps in the process of building theory.

This research is limited to case studies on public organizations in Indonesia that have undergone organizational transformation from traditional organizations to Team of Teams structures. We only take one case study of organizational transformation in the West Java Provincial Government together with stakeholders involved such as the head of the service, head of the division, and also the team leader. In total, we conducted interviews with 3 people with an average of 48 minutes.

From the study in the West Java Provincial Government, we examine insights from stakeholders involved in organizational transformation, including the Regional Secretary of West Java Province. Compared to other public organizations, the West Java Provincial Government has implemented organizational transformation through the Team of Teams approach across all organizations under it, including departments, agencies, and bureaus. The West Java Provincial Government is the first government organization to implement Team of Teams.

The West Java Provincial Government is also a public organization serving a province with the largest population in Indonesia, which is 50.35 million people in 2023 (CNBC Indonesia, 2024). From an organizational perspective, the number of Civil Servants (PNS) at the provincial level in the West Java Provincial Government is also the largest compared to PNS in other provinces, reaching 30,301 employees in 2024 (BPS Jabar, 2024). Research in the West Java Provincial Government will provide insight into how to formulate the Team of Teams model in public organizations for the Indonesian context.

Among the 46 bureaus, agencies, and services under the scope of the West Java Provincial Government, One-Stop Integrated Investment Service of West Java Province (next called Dinas Penanaman Modal Terpadu Satu Pintu or DPMPTSP of West Java) was chosen as the object of research because it has a strategic role in developing infrastructure and regional economic development. As one of the provinces with the largest population in Indonesia, DPMPTSP of West Java faces many challenges in order to provide efficient, fast, and public satisfaction-oriented licensing and investment services. Therefore, DPMPTSP of West Java is the main pillar to maintain and increase investment value in West Java through technology-based licensing management and cross-work unit collaboration.

According to Regulation of the Governor of West Java Number 62 of 2016 regarding the Main Tasks, Functions, Details of Unit Tasks, and Work Procedures of the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office, the DPMPTSP of West Java Province is responsible for the following responsibilities: (a) fostering an investment climate, (b) promoting investment, (c) serving investment, and (d) administering investment data and information systems.

In the second quarter of 2024, West Java province became the first in investment realization with a combined investment value of foreign investment (Penanaman Modal Asing or PMA) and domestic investment (Penanaman Modal Dalam Negeri or PMDN) of IDR 63.66 trillion (Humas Jabar, 2024). There are 5 countries with the highest investment value in West Java from January to June 2024. Based on the data, Singapore has the highest investment value, with IDR 19,14 trillion, followed by Japan and South Korea, with IDR 16,29 trillion and IDR 9,563 trillion consecutively (Pamungkas, 2024). On the other hand, according to Muhamad (2024), the next province with the highest investment value is DKI Jakarta (IDR 62 trillion), East Java (IDR 35,6 trillion), Banten (IDR 33 trillion), and Central Sulawesi (IDR 32,8 trillion).

4. Results

Qualitative extracts from the interviews conducted highlighted several important areas, including identifying conditions prior to the implementation of Team of Teams and identifying conditions after the implementation of Team of Teams.

4.1. Conditions before the implementation of Team of Teams

The traditional structure in DPMPTSP of West Java is illustrated in Figure 2, with the head of the agency at the highest level. There is a department that is led by the chief of the department and is located below the head of the agency. The functional position group is situated adjacent to the department and comprises a variety of functional positions within the agency. Numerous sections are located beneath the department. In this instance, the development and promotion department is divided into three sections: the development and policy section, the promotion and cooperation section, and the facilitation section.

Figure 2: DPMPTSP of West Java with Traditional Structure before bureaucratic simplification

Source: DPMPTSP of West Java

In this situation, DPMPTSP of West Java province operates within a hierarchical structure, following a vertical and formal command flow from top to bottom. Consequently, executives possess limited capacity for innovation or decision-making. Strategic decisions must be made by the Head of Service, an Echelon 2 official, and thereafter communicated to the Head of Division, an Echelon 3 official, and the Head of Section, an Echelon 4 official. Subsequently, personnel in each department will execute the decision. The DPMPTSP of West Java comprises 6 personnel at the echelon 3 level and 18 employees at the echelon 4 level, omitting structural authorities at the technical implementing unit level. This represents the state of the organizational structure prior to the implementation of bureaucratic simplification.

The DPMPTSP of West Java executes coordination that emphasizes operational functions, indicating that task execution and decision-making are aligned with the organizational division of labor. Employees in the development and policy division only concentrate on their designated tasks and do not assist colleagues in the promotion and cooperation division or the facilitation division while operating within the same field. This scenario fosters a silo mentality that obstructs communication and collaboration within departments and disciplines.

Leaders at all tiers within DPMPTSP of West Java function as directors and controllers by establishing directives, overseeing performance, managing resources, and making decisions. Since leaders predominantly make decisions, other employees possess limited autonomy in executing their responsibilities, resulting in minimal flexibility for innovation. The consequence is that the organization struggles to adapt swiftly to change, employee enthusiasm and inventiveness diminish due to diminished involvement in decision-making, and the decision-making process is sluggish.

4.2. Conditions after the implementation of Team of Teams

Before carrying out institutional transformation with the Team of Teams approach, the DPMPTSP of West Java followed the direction of the President of the Republic of Indonesia to simplify the bureaucracy by equalizing positions for echelon 4 officials to become functional officials. Thus, there are no longer any work units at the section level under each field in the DPMPTSP of West Java, as shown in

Figure 3. All employees in the same field can work together without being divided based on section differences. Currently, the existing structural officials are 1 head of agency as echelon 2 officials and 6 heads of departments as echelon 3 officials. With this bureaucratic simplification, the command flow is reduced to only two levels from the previous three levels, thus accelerating the command flow and communication. Nonetheless, the implementation of bureaucratic structures requires enhancement for the organization to function adaptively.

Figure 3: DPMPTSP of West Java with Traditional Structure After Bureaucratic Simplification

Source: DPMPTSP of West Java

After simplifying the bureaucracy, DPMPTSP of West Java is moving towards a more flexible organization by implementing a competency-based grouping called Team of Teams. With this approach, all employees within the scope of DPMPTSP of West Java are grouped based on their specific expertise, not only seen from administrative tasks or divided according to field or work unit, as shown in

Figure 4. In the agency, there are 9 competency groups, namely 1. Photo and video production expertise, 2. News coverage expertise, 3. Social media management expertise, 4. Leadership protocol expertise, 5. Exploring investment opportunities expertise, 6. Investor relation expertise, 7. Collaborative expertise, 8. Monitoring and evaluation expertise, 9. Human resource development expertise. Each competency group consists of members from different departments. For example, the photo and video production expertise is comprised of members from various departments who share a common interest and level of expertise. While engaged in their task, members of the expertise collaborate with individuals from other groups.

Figure 4: Grouping based on competency in DPMPTSP of West Java

Source: DPMPTSP of West Java

DPMPTSP of West Java has several strategic activities that are routinely held every year or held incidentally. These activities are related to public services, especially those related to promotion and investment in West Java Province. Figure 5 below are several activities that the agency holds. The main activities that are shown are: 1. Investment promotion activities, 2. Management West Java Investment Hub (WJIH) activities, 3. SOP drafting activities, 4. West Java Investment Summit event, 5. Collaborative event, and 6. Investment potential map preparation event. From the picture it is known that each activity consists of several teams. The activities with the most teams are investment promotion activities and West Java Investment Summit activities, each consisting of 8 teams. The activity with the fewest teams is the collaborative activity, which consists of 3 teams.

Figure 5: Main Activities in DPMPTSP of West Java
 Source: DPMPTSP of West Java

Figure 6 below shows the relationship between all activities carried out at DPMPTSP of West Java and the teams that support these activities. Each expertise team connects with several activities, and each activity consists of several expertise teams. In this way, strong collaboration is created between teams that can support the success of an activity.

Figure 6: The Relationship Between All Activities and All Teams
 Source: DPMPTSP of West Java

5. Discussion

This study indicates that the work environment of civil servants at DPMPTSP of West Java meets the definition of Team of Teams. The insights and descriptions provided by public servants are consistent with the definition of Team of Teams and speak to cross-sector coordination and minimal silos between work units (McChrystal et al., 2015; Melsop et al., 2019; Young et al., 2016). Furthermore, participants also showed that their working methods were more flexible and they were also given space to make decisions and innovate. One of the advantages of implementing competency-based grouping or Team of Teams in DPMPTSP West Java is the creation of a closer and more synergistic relationship between the various main activities in DPMPTSP West Java. This system encourages more intensive interaction between teams and allows for faster and more accurate information exchange (Alqudah & Razali, 2016). For example, the team responsible for material preparation can communicate directly with the data and analysis team so that unity and similarity of data are created at the team level. Furthermore, the implementation of Team of Teams provides new dynamics and atmosphere in the organizational work pattern in DPMPTSP West Java. All employees are expected to work more actively and show innovations in their work. On the other hand, employees still have to adjust to a new and more dynamic work culture (Saarikallio & Tyrväinen, 2023).

Similarities were observed between the agile conditions of organizations as described by Vaszkun & Sziráki (2023) and those in public organizations. There are three things to create an agile organization, namely organizational structure, work culture, and leadership. Interestingly, in the context where Team of Teams as an agile organization approach discussed in this study can also be applied to highly bureaucratic and hierarchical organizations such as public organizations in Indonesia. Conversely, institutional transformation via the Team of Teams methodology in Indonesian public organizations is facilitated by the simplification of bureaucracy, reducing the bureaucratic hierarchy from three levels to two (Saksono et al., 2024).

The research findings indicate that transforming the organizational culture in public entities from a walled structure to a more collaborative framework is inherently challenging. The Team of Teams methodology, particularly through the utilization of competency-based groups illustrated in Figure 7, necessitates that each employee actively collaborates with colleagues from other work units while consistently enhancing their skills.

Figure 7: Implementation of Team of Teams Approach Using Competency-Based Groups

Moreover, the institutional shift from a bureaucratic organization to a Team of Teams was contingent upon robust support from the highest authority in the West Java Provincial Government, specifically the Regional Secretary as an echelon 1 structural official. The Regional Secretary of West Java Province, in collaboration with the Organization Bureau, Regional Personnel Agency, and Legal Bureau, established the Team of Teams approach, which is implemented across all 46 bureaus, services, and agencies within the West Java Provincial government. This is in accordance with the research findings of Almahasneh et al. (2023) that changes in organizational structure and culture can be carried out with the direction of leaders which is stated in regulations. These findings have significant implications for the agile organization and Team of Teams literature, indicating that the establishment of competency-based groups must be accompanied by a thorough comprehension of each employee's skill. We recommend that future research on Team of Teams focus more intently on the collaboration of expertise among teams and the influence of individual behaviors on the performance of the Team of Teams.

6. Practical Implication

The results of this investigation hold significant significance for future practice. This document emphasizes essential insights that may assist civil servants in a public organization engaged in a Team of Teams framework.

6.1 *Coordination across sectors and disciplines grounded in essential competencies*

The effective implementation of Team of Teams relies on intersectoral and interdisciplinary collaboration (Melsop et al., 2019; Young et al., 2016). This coordination is mostly dependent on individual skills relevant to certain activities. Therefore, team members must actively improve current competencies or obtain new skills necessary for effective collaboration. Public organizations may provide training programs, workshops, or project-based learning to promote this development.

6.2 *Enhancing leadership to guide a diverse team*

In Team of Teams, the leader's role deviates from the traditional hierarchical structure. Leaders are not just selected based on previous organizational positions; instead, they are appointed for their ability to manage, inspire, and coordinate diverse teams. Leaders within a Team of Teams should prioritize the development of charisma and authentic leadership skills (Connaughton, 2016). This can be achieved through empathy-focused leadership training, effective communication, and inclusive decision-making. This charisma is crucial for ensuring that their counsel is recognized and followed by all team members, especially in the absence of a formal hierarchy.

7. Limitations

The limitation of this study is that this study uses single case studies from public organizations in Indonesia, where only one agency out of 46 agencies, agencies, and bureaus under the scope of the West Java Provincial Government is used as a case study. Furthermore, the case raised in this study has limitations, namely the results of the study do not consider interpersonal dynamics between team members.

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that the legacy culture of public organizations constantly challenges the complexity of Team of Teams. The challenges, as we have shown, however, continue to occur at the individual level, both in behavioral and cognitive aspects, which have not previously been studied in the case of public organizations. Our findings also suggest that civil servants need to have a broader perspective, including knowledge of how to collaborate effectively across disciplines and also the relationships between different organizations and individuals. Further research into the interconnectedness of Team of Teams and how team members work together in complex environments would be beneficial for both practitioners and academics. The more we can investigate and understand the behavior of civil servants working in Team of Teams environments, the more we can improve our understanding from both a scientific and a practical perspective.

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